

Scientific Cruise Report

Cruise EL25 – R/V Electra 17-21 August and 26-27 August 2025.

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1. Cruise participants

There were 11 participants (researchers) in the cruise:

Name	Affiliation	Role
Marcelo Ketzer	Linnaeus University	Co-chief scientist
Christian Stranne	Stockholm University	Co-chief scientist
Changxun Yu	Linnaeus University	Geochemical sampling
Melissa Sundberg	Linnaeus University	Geochemical sampling
Christoph Böttner	Stockholm University	Seismic acquisition
Elias Erstorp	Stockholm University	Seismic acquisition
Camile Akhoudas	Stockholm University	Sea-air measurements with WEGAS system
Yvonne Yau	Stockholm University	Sea-air measurements with WEGAS system
Satoko Owari	Tokyo University of Marine Science and Technology	Geochemical sampling
Gerald Dickens	Trinity College Dublin	Geochemical sampling
Frederico Rodrigues	Utrecht University and UNISINOS, Brazil	Geochemical sampling

2. Aim of the cruise

The main objective of the cruise was to investigate the Southern Quark drift deposit and the possible methane ebullition in the area. The plan was to make acoustic surveys (mid-water sonar and seismics) and profiles of the water column with CTD. In addition, we also aimed at obtaining water samples with niskin bottles (CTD) and sediment samples with gravity- and multi-cores. We also included the Landsort Deep area in this cruise for comparison as it is a known ebullition site in the Baltic Sea (same objectives listed above). We dedicated five days of the cruise in the Southern Quark area (17-21 August 2025 – LEG 1) using the Grisslehamn harbour and two days in the Landsort Deep area (26-27 August 2025 – LEG 2) using the Äskö harbour. A total of seven stations with multiple operations were executed in Southern Quark (5) and Landsort Deep (2). See Figure 1 for location.

Fig. 1 – Location map of the two areas investigated during the EL25 cruise (Southern Quark and Landsort Deep).

3. Cruise summary

LEG 1 – Southern Quark

Day 1 – 16 August 2025

Transit from Äskö to Grisslehamn.

Day 2 – 17 August 2025

Downtime weather. Test of ROV and seismic equipment in the harbour.

Day 3 – 18 August 2025

Midwater sonar survey lines in the Southern Quark drift. Deployment of the mid-water sonar station on the seafloor (site 1). Multi-core, gravity core, and CTD in site 1 (see Fig. 2 for locations).

Day 4 – 19 August 2025

Gravity core and CTD in site 2 (see Fig. 2 for locations).

Day 5 – 20 August 2025

Multi-core site 2. Gravity core in site 3. Seismic acquisition. ROV dive 1 (see Fig. 2 for locations).

Day 6 – 21 August 2025

ROV dive 2. Seismic acquisition. Gravity core and CTD in site 4. Multi-cores in sites 3 and 5 (see Fig. 2 for locations).

Day 7 – 22 August 2025

Transit from Grisslehamn to Äskö.

LEG 2 – Landsort Deep

Day 8 – 26 August 2025

Mid-water sonar survey. Gravity core, and CTD in site 6 (see Fig. 2 for locations). Problems during coring with multi-corer in site 6 (overpenetration of the instrument into sediments – lack of bottom water in the core).

Day 9 – 27 August 2025

Adjustment of the multi-corer - installation of “wings” and removal of weights to prevent overpenetration in the sediment. Adjustments worked out and coring was possible. Multi-core in site 6. Multi-core, gravity core, and CTD in site 7 (see Fig. 2 for locations).

Fig. 2 – Location map of seismic and mid-water sonar survey lines, and stations for CTD and coring operations in Southern Quark (A) and Landsort Deep (B) areas. Numbers indicate the core and CTD stations.

4. Scientific objectives

The marine environment is an important source of atmospheric methane with most of the emissions occurring in coastal areas. This is in part related to the fact that the vast quantities of methane produced in deep marine sediments are consumed or “microbially filtered” by anaerobic oxidation of methane with sulphate below the seafloor. However, methane migration in sediments as gas bubbles can largely by-pass the microbial filter and escape on the seafloor. Methane bubbles may reach the atmosphere in shallow waters but will dissolve and oxidize in deep waters (>100 m) before reaching the sea surface². That is why the vast area of open oceans only contribute to a small fraction (i.e., <10%) of the atmospheric methane input from the marine environment.

Up to the present, the atmospheric methane input from the Baltic Sea is considered to follow the same rationale as above, i.e., that most of the emissions are linked to coastal areas. This is because there were no known ebullition sites in the deep Baltic Sea until now, and the water column in deep settings is considered as an efficient barrier to prevent that methane in bottom waters reaches the sea surface. The water column contains two very distinct water masses separated by a permanent halocline at ca. 60-80 m of depth: the saline, oxygen depleted, and methane-rich bottom water, and the fresher, oxygenated, and methane-poorer surface water. The reason for the contrasting methane concentrations in bottom and surface waters is the limited quantity of methane produced “in-situ” in the surface water and the efficient microbial oxidation that aerobically consumes most of methane dissolved in the water just below the halocline. High methane concentrations in bottom waters are maintained via a continuous gas resupply from the sediments, notably in areas with high rate of sediment accumulation.

Occasionally, methane concentrations in Baltic Sea bottom waters are drastically reduced during the invasion of seawater from the North Sea or seasonal mixing with oxygenated waters. However, concentration quickly returns to the original values after few months indicating a rapid resupply from sediments. Methane is believed to be sourced from sediments mostly via diffusion. This diffusion hypothesis, however, leads to a fundamental problem: anaerobic oxidation of methane should “filter” and prevent any significant diffusive methane flux from sediment to bottom water. Our previous data from the Landsort Deep, based on hull-mounted and seafloor-mounted broadband sonar data, indicate that methane bubbles venting out from the seafloor rise through the entire water column and reach the sea surface and, consequently, contributes to an unknown (hence unaccounted) direct source of methane to the atmosphere. This important observation urged a revision of the idea that atmospheric methane emissions from the Baltic Sea mainly originate from coastal areas. Our data also suggest that ebullition is spatially related to anomalously thick Holocene sediment deposits formed by bottom currents. These currents efficiently sort and accumulate fine-grained, organic-rich deposits in thick contourite drifts. These deposits would be the loci of vigorous methanogenesis that would eventually generate sufficient methane to reach supersaturation that, in turn, vents as free gas on the seafloor. If this hypothesis is correct, there are several other potential ebullition sites in the deep Baltic Sea yet to be discovered. Interestingly, we have recently observed bubbles rising from the seafloor in the Southern Quark region (Åland Sea), which consists of a thick deposit formed by bottom currents. An additional important point to consider is that a significant portion of the bubbles in the Landsort Deep site rise >200 m in the

water column and do not reach the atmosphere owing to the water depth in the area (>400 m). However, it is possible to speculate that bubbles will reach the atmosphere in other ebullition sites occurring in shallower waters. That is one of the main reasons to focus our investigation in the Southern Quark area.

We planned to obtain acoustic images of the water column and seismic profiles to characterize the ebullition sites. We also planned to acquire samples to measure methane concentrations and other parameters (e.g., sulphate) in the water (CTD/Rosette) and in sediments (gravity/piston/multi-cores). Sampling methods were adapted from Ketzer et al. (2024; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2024.107220>). Cores will be logged at Stockholm University and geochemical analyses will be performed at the stable isotope laboratory at Linnaeus University.

5. Station/activities log

The expedition was divided in two legs. Leg 1 activities comprised five stations in the Southern Quark area (18-21 August 2025; see Fig. 2 for location). Seismic surveys were executed on 20-21 August 2025 (Southern Quark) and on 27 August 2025 (Landsort Deep), while mid-water sonar surveys were executed on 19-20 August 2025 (Southern Quark) and on 27 August 2025 in Landsort Deep. The surveys with ADCP (Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler) and WEGAS (Water Equilibration Gas Analyser System) systems were executed continuously during the entire expedition. Below we present the details of each of the operations executed in the seven stations comprised during this cruise:

Station Test		
ID		Comments: Downtime weather in the morning (winds up to 25 m/s). Test of the seismic equipment and ROV in a protected area outside the Grisslehamn harbour. Weather improved in the afternoon and we could start the mission.
Operation	Seismic and ROV	
Date	18-Aug-25	
Aim	Test of equipment	
Water depth		
Latitude	60°5.832'	
Longitude	018°49,177'	

Station 1 LEG 1		
ID	EL25_WBAT	Comments: Deployment of the mid-water seafloor station in the center of the ebullition field (highest bubbling intensity in the hull-mounted mid-water sonar). The station will be retrieved at the end of LEG 1.
Operation	Mid-water seafloor station	
Date	18-Aug-25	
Aim	Southern Quark drift (center)	
Water depth	172 m	
Latitude	60°20.981'	
Longitude	018°58.699'	

Station 1		LEG 1
ID	EL25_CTD1	Comments: CTD profile with collection of 12 water samples at the following depths (m): 170, 160, 140, 120, 110, 100, 90, 70, 50, 25, 10, 0. Inside ebullition field (center).
Operation	CTD	
Date	18-Aug-25	
Aim	Southern Quark drift (center)	
Water depth	172 m	
Latitude	60°20.981'	
Longitude	018°58.699'	

Station 1		LEG 1
ID	EL25_GC1	Comments: Recovery 3.56 m. Inside ebullition field (center). Core cut in 1 m-long sections and transported to Stockholm University.
Operation	Gravity core	
Date	18-Aug-25	
Aim	Southern Quark drift (center)	
Water depth	172 m	
Latitude	60°20.981'	
Longitude	018°58.699'	

Station 1		LEG 1
ID	EL25_MC1	Comments: Recovery 41 cm. Inside ebullition field (center). Core sliced and sampled onboard.
Operation	Multi-core GMAX	
Date	18-Aug-25	
Aim	Southern Quark drift (center)	
Water depth	172 m	
Latitude	60°20.981'	
Longitude	018°58.699'	

Station 1		LEG 1
ID	EL25_ROV1	Comments: ROV Dive 1 located inside the ebullition field (center). Operation took ca. 3 hours. Very fine grained material on the seafloor. Poor visibility. Linear marks on the seafloor formed by bentic fauna. Not possible to locate/sample bubble stream owing to their effemeral character (few seconds?). They were identify in the ROV sonar. We tried to disturb the seafloor with a stick (0.5 m long) but it was not possible to cause ebullition.
Operation	ROV	
Date	20-Aug-25	
Aim	Southern Quark drift (center)	
Water depth	172 m	
Latitude	60°20.981'	
Longitude	018°58.699'	

Station 1		LEG 1
ID	EL25_ROV2	Comments: ROV Dive 2 located inside the ebullition field (center) at ca. 100 m from the location of Dive 1 (strongest ebullition in the mid-water sonar). Operation took ca. 3 hours. Similar experience as in Dive 1. Very fine grained material on the see floor. Poor visibility. Linear marks on the seafloor formed by bentic fauna. Not possible to locate/sample bubble stream owing to their effemeral character (few seconds?). They were identify in the ROV sonar. We tried to disturb the seafloor with a stick (0.5 m long) but it was not possible to cause ebullition.
Operation	ROV	
Date	21-Aug-25	
Aim	Southern Quark drift (center)	
Water depth	172 m	
Latitude	60°21.043'	
Longitude	018°58.6745'	

Station 2		LEG 1
ID	EL25_CTD2	Comments: CTD profile with collection of 12 water samples at the following depths (m): 190, 180, 160, 140, 120, 110, 100, 90, 70, 50, 25, 0. Outside ebullition field (edge).
Operation	CTD	
Date	19-Aug-25	
Aim	Southern Quark drift (edge)	
Water depth	199 m	
Latitude	60°21.341'	
Longitude	018°58.788'	

Station 2		LEG 1
ID	EL25_GC2	Comments: Recovery 4.31 m. Outside ebullition field (edge). Core cut in 1 m-long sections and transported to Stockholm University.
Operation	Gravity core	
Date	19-Aug-25	
Aim	Southern Quark drift (edge)	
Water depth	199 m	
Latitude	60°21.341'	
Longitude	018°58.788'	

Station 2		LEG 1
ID	EL25_MC2	Comments: Recovery 15 cm. Very short core possibly because of sandy sediment. Outside ebullition field (edge). Core sliced and sampled onboard.
Operation	Multi-core GMAX	
Date	20-Aug-25	
Aim	Southern Quark drift (edge)	
Water depth	199 m	
Latitude	60°21.341'	
Longitude	018°58.788'	

Station 3		LEG 1
ID	EL25_GC3	Comments: Recovery 3.40 m. Inside ebullition field (edge). Core cut in 1 m-long sections and transported to Stockholm University.
Operation	Gravity core	
Date	20-Aug-25	
Aim	Southern Quark drift (edge)	
Water depth	179 m	
Latitude	60°21.196'	
Longitude	018°58.754'	

Station 3		LEG 1
ID	EL25_MC3	Comments: Recovery 45 cm. The site is inside the main ebullition field (edge). Core sliced and sampled onboard.
Operation	Multi-core GMAX	
Date	21-Aug-25	
Aim	Southern Quark drift (edge)	
Water depth	179 m	
Latitude	60°21.196'	
Longitude	018°58.754'	

Station 4		LEG 1
ID	EL25_GC4	Comments: Recovery 4.01 m. This station was aimed for a background/reference site, outside ebullition field. However, some ebullition activity was detected in the mid-water sonar (possibly a smaller drift?). Core cut in 1 m-long sections and transported to Stockholm University.
Operation	Gravity core	
Date	21-Aug-25	
Aim	Southern Quark drift (background)	
Water depth	192 m	
Latitude	60°22.840'	
Longitude	018°54.706'	

Station 4		LEG 1
ID	EL25_CTD4	Comments: CTD profile with collection of 12 water samples at the following depths (m): 185, 180, 160, 140, 120, 110, 100, 90, 70, 50, 25, 0. Outside ebullition field (background).
Operation	CTD	
Date	21-Aug-25	
Aim	Southern Quark drift (background)	
Water depth	192 m	
Latitude	60°22.840'	
Longitude	018°54.706'	

Station 5		LEG 1
ID	EL25_MC5	Comments: Recovery 22 cm. Very short core possibly because of sandy sediment. The site is outside the main ebullition field (NW) but contains a very strong ebullition signal in the mid-water sonar. Core sliced and sampled onboard.
Operation	Multi-core GMAX	
Date	21-Aug-25	
Aim	Southern Quark drift (background)	
Water depth	177 m	
Latitude	60°22.1332'	
Longitude	018°57.1587'	

Leg 2 activities comprised two stations in the Landsort Deep area (26-27 August 2025; see Fig. 2 for location):

Station 6		LEG 2
ID	EL25_CTD6	Comments: CTD profile with collection of 12 water samples at the following depths (m): 400, 385, 350, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 75, 50, 10, 0. Inside the ebullition field (center). Same location of expeditions MOS20 (site SE-08) and EL23 (site 2).
Operation	CTD	
Date	26-Aug-25	
Aim	Landsort Deep drift (center)	
Water depth	409 m	
Latitude	58°40.689'	
Longitude	018°21.394'	

Station 6		LEG 2
ID	EL25_GC6	Comments: Recovery 4.52 m. Gas expansion inside the core. Core cut in 1 m-long sections and transported to Stockholm University.
Operation	Gravity core	
Date	26-Aug-25	
Aim	Landsort Deep drift (center)	
Water depth	409 m	
Latitude	58°40.689'	
Longitude	018°21.394'	

Station 6		LEG 2
ID	EL25_MC6	Comments: Recovery 52 cm. Many gas bubbles found in inside the core. Difficulties to core owing to gassy and soupy character of the sediment. Core sliced and sampled onboard.
Operation	Multi-core GMAX	
Date	27-Aug-25	
Aim	Landsort Deep drift (center)	
Water depth	409 m	
Latitude	58°40.689'	
Longitude	018°21.394'	

Station 7		LEG 2
ID	EL25_CTD7	Comments: CTD profile with collection of 12 water samples at the following depths (m): 441, 400, 350, 300, 250, 200, 150, 100, 70, 50, 25, 0. Channel feature in the Landsort Deep. Site at the same location of IODP expedition 347 (site M0063). Weak ebullition activity found in mid-water sonar.
Operation	CTD	
Date	27-Aug-25	
Aim	Landsort Deep drift (channel)	
Water depth	441 m	
Latitude	58°37.364'	
Longitude	018°15.270'	

Station 7		LEG 2
ID	EL25_MC7	Comments: Recovery 59 cm. Channel feature in the Landsort Deep. Site at the same location of IODP expedition 347 (site M0063). Weak ebullition activity found in mid-water sonar. Gas bubbles found inside the core. Core sliced and sampled onboard.
Operation	Multi-core GMAX	
Date	27-Aug-25	
Aim	Landsort Deep drift (channel)	
Water depth	441 m	
Latitude	58°37.364'	
Longitude	018°15.270'	

Station 7		LEG 2
ID	EL25_GC7	Comments: Recovery 2.72 m. Channel feature in the Landsort Deep. Site at the same location of IODP expedition 347 (site M0063). Weak ebullition activity found in mid-water sonar. Gas bubbles found inside the core. Core cut in 1 m-long sections and transported to Stockholm University.
Operation	Gravity core	
Date	27-Aug-25	
Aim	Landsort Deep drift (channel)	
Water depth	441 m	
Latitude	58°37.364'	
Longitude	018°15.270'	

6. Data document sheet

We have acquired ca. 34 km of seismic lines and ca. 27 km of mid-water sonar lines. In addition, we have collected 6 gravity cores (22.5 m), 6 multi-cores (233 cm), and 5 CTDs. These operations resulted in a total of 201 samples for gas analyses (headspace gas for molecular and stable isotopic composition), 141 samples for porewater chemistry (e.g., sulphate, DIC, DOC, $d^{13}C_{DIC}$, $d^{13}C_{DOC}$), 115 sediment samples for diverse analyses (e.g., TOC, and $d^{13}C_{TOC}$), and 60 seawater samples for chemical analyses (e.g., sulphate, DIC, DOC, $d^{13}C_{DIC}$, $d^{13}C_{DOC}$). The chart below summarises the data acquired during the cruise:

Data type	Location	ID	Quantity	Storage	Availability*	Gas	Por	Sed	Wat	Comments
Seismic lines	Southern Quark		12 km	Stockholm University	Upon request after evaluation					
Seismic lines	Landsort Deep		22 km	Stockholm University	Upon request after evaluation					
Mid-water sonar lines	Southern Quark		9 km	Stockholm University	Upon request after evaluation					
Mid-water sonar lines	Landsort Deep		18 km	Stockholm University	Upon request after evaluation					
Mid-water sonar seafloor	Southern Quark		4 days	Stockholm University	Upon request after evaluation					Seafloor station with mid-water sonar WBAT.
Gravity core	Southern Quark	EL25_GC1	3.56 m	Stockholm University	Upon request after evaluation	4	4			Sampled onboard. Core to be split in Stockholm
Gravity core	Southern Quark	EL25_GC2	4.31 m	Stockholm University	Upon request after evaluation	5	5			Sampled onboard. Core to be split in Stockholm
Gravity core	Southern Quark	EL25_GC3	3.4 m	Stockholm University	Upon request after evaluation	4	4			Sampled onboard. Core to be split in Stockholm
Gravity core	Southern Quark	EL25_GC4	4.01 m	Stockholm University	Upon request after evaluation	4	4			Sampled onboard. Core to be split in Stockholm
Gravity core	Landsort Deep	EL25_GC6	4.52 m	Stockholm University	Upon request after evaluation	5	5			Sampled onboard. Core to be split in Stockholm
Gravity core	Landsort Deep	EL25_GC7	2.72 m	Stockholm University	Upon request after evaluation	4	4			Sampled onboard. Core to be split in Stockholm
Multi-core	Southern Quark	EL25_MC1	41 cm	Linnaeus University	Upon request after evaluation	20	20	20		Core sliced/sampled onboard
Multi-core	Southern Quark	EL25_MC2	15 cm	Linnaeus University	Upon request after evaluation	7	7	7		Core sliced/sampled onboard
Multi-core	Southern Quark	EL25_MC3	45 cm	Linnaeus University	Upon request after evaluation	22	22	22		Core sliced/sampled onboard
Multi-core	Southern Quark	EL25_MC5	22 cm	Linnaeus University	Upon request after evaluation	11	11	11		Core sliced/sampled onboard
Multi-core	Landsort Deep	EL25_MC6	52 cm	Linnaeus University	Upon request after evaluation	26	26	26		Core sliced/sampled onboard
Multi-core	Landsort Deep	EL25_MC7	59 cm	Linnaeus University	Upon request after evaluation	29	29	29		Core sliced/sampled onboard
CTD	Southern Quark	EL25_CTD1	12 bottles	Linnaeus University	Upon request after evaluation	12			12	Samples collected onboard
CTD	Southern Quark	EL25_CTD2	12 bottles	Linnaeus University	Upon request after evaluation	12			12	Samples collected onboard
CTD	Southern Quark	EL25_CTD4	12 bottles	Linnaeus University	Upon request after evaluation	12			12	Samples collected onboard
CTD	Landsort Deep	EL25_CTD6	12 bottles	Linnaeus University	Upon request after evaluation	12			12	Samples collected onboard
CTD	Landsort Deep	EL25_CTD7	12 bottles	Linnaeus University	Upon request after evaluation	12			12	Samples collected onboard
Totals						Totals	201	141	115	60
34 km seismic (14 lines)						Gas	gas samples (headspace)			
27 km mid-water sonar (13 lines)						Por	Pore-water samples			
22.5 m of gravity cores (6 units)						Sed	Sediment samples			
233 cm of multi-cores (6 units)						Wat	Seawater samples			

*Data linked to a VR project (no. 2024-04662) coordinated by Marceto Ketzner.

7. Instruments, methods, and preliminary results

The following instruments and methods were used during the expedition:

Mid-water sonar: Midwater split-beam sonar EK80, 70 kHz/200 kHz

Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP): Workhorse Mariner, 600 kHz (range up to 150 m)

Water Equilibration Gas Analyser System (WEGAS): refer to Humborg et al. (2019)

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00493>

Conductivity Temperature Depth (CTD): Seabird 911+, 12 x 5L, O₂, turbidity, CDOM, ChlA sensors

Coring: 6 m-long gravity corer and 70 cm-long GMAX multi-corer.

Geochemistry: refer to Ketzner et al. (2024) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2024.107220>

Seismics: We used an ultra-high resolution seismic sparker system by SIG France to image the upper sedimentary succession up to ~120 m below the seafloor. The system comprises of a SIG Pulse L5 power supply (100-6000 Joules), an ELP790 antenna (50 tips) and a two-channel seismic streamer with a hydrophone spacing of 6 x 0.2 m for channel 1 and 8 x 0.75 m for channel 2. The system was towed 20 m behind the stern of the ship with the sparker tied to inner side of the A-Frame (-8.6 m along the ship from antenna) on portside (+0.8 m across the ship from GPS antenna) and the streamer on starboard side (-3.3 m across the ship from GPS). The

sparker generally produces frequencies between 100-3500 Hz. The main frequency depends, however, on the power settings. Lower power (300 J) resulted in relatively high main frequency of 700 Hz. After initial testing, we mainly used high power output (1000 J) which generated relatively low main frequency of ~350 Hz, resulting in good penetration and quality of recorded data.

Most of the acoustic data (mid-water sonar and seismic) is still under a processing phase. Preliminary, the mid-water sonar survey confirmed the existence of ebullition in the Southern Quark drift as anticipated. The ebullition is focused mostly on the main drift (Fig. 3), but other gas seeps have been identified outside the limits of the structure. The results also showed that ebullition still happens in the Landsort Deep site with a similar intensity as the one observed in the previous cruise (EL23, August 2023). The limits of the ebullition field in Landsort Deep also didn't change from 2023 and 2025.

Fig. 3 – Mid-water sonar images showing the ebullition across the Southern Quark area. Note that the gas bubbles are mostly limited to the drift deposit forming an elevation on the seafloor.

Preliminary visualisation of the seismic lines (unprocessed) confirmed the hypothesis that both the Southern Quark and Landsort Deep areas are formed typically by contourite drifts showing an elevation on the seafloor caused by thickening of the sediments. The seismic lines also show amplitude anomalies at shallow depths below the seafloor (few meters) caused by free gas (Fig. 4).

The geochemistry work is still under progress: molecular and isotopic composition of gases, chemistry of pore waters and seawaters, and geochemistry of the solid sediment phase. Preliminary results show that the gas present in sediments is essentially formed by methane and carbon dioxide. High concentrations of methane (ca. 20 mM) were found in both ebullition areas, Southern Quark and Landsort Deep. Isotopic analyses revealed that methane is predominantly of microbial origin (i.e., $d^{13}C < -60$ per mil) in both areas. Data from ADCP and WEGAS systems are still in the processing phase and there are no preliminary results to be shown at this point.

Fig. 4 – Seismic images showing sediment structures typical of contourite drifts in the Southern Quark (A) and Landsort Deep (B) areas. Note the presence of shallow gas in sediments (high amplitude anomalies).

We expected that the EL23 cruise will contribute to the following publications/topics:

1. Geochemical characterization of the ebullition system of the Southern Quark area
2. Quantification of seafloor methane emissions in the Southern Quark area
3. Characterization of the contourite drifts of the deep Baltic Sea environment
4. Time series monitoring of the ebullition field in the Landsort Deep (expeditions in 2020, 2023, and 2025).

Our Data Management Plan will follow the strategy commonly used in many projects at Stockholm University. We will store our data in the Bolin Centre Database, which is an open access platform and can be easily accessed at the website (<https://bolin.su.se/data/>). This

database is designed to safely store all type of complex datasets from large and small projects. We will store acoustic and sensors raw and processed data after the mission. Information about sediment cores and CTD (conductivity, temperature, depth) casts will be stored soon after the mission. Specific analyses performed after the mission in laboratory (e.g., methane, sulphate, isotopes) will be published according to the development of the project. All publications resulting from the mission will be submitted to open access journals and linked to the Bolin Centre Database.